

Predicting the Progress and Outcome of Labor Using a New Sonographic Index Occiput Spine Angle in a Tertiary Care Hospital, Madurai**R. Gnanapriya¹, Mahalakshmi P², K.S. Chitra³, Ramya A⁴, Udhayarajapriya R⁵, Sriandaal Venkateshvaran⁶**¹Assistant Professor, Velammal Medical College and Research Center, Madurai²Final Year Post Graduate, Velammal Medical College and Research Center, Madurai³Professor & HOD, Department of OBGYN, Velammal Medical College and Research Center, Madurai⁴Senior Resident, Velammal Medical College and Research Center, Madurai⁵Second Year Post Graduate, Velammal Medical College and Research Center, Madurai⁶Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Velammal Medical College and Research Center, Madurai

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Corresponding Author: Dr. R. Gnanapriya

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Abstract:**Background:** Universal flexion is the most common attitude of the fetus at birth which allows normal progression of labor. The attitude of the fetus head during the active phase of labor is generally identified by per vaginal digital examination. Recently a newer ultrasound parameter, Occiput spine angle can aid our conventional clinical examination to assess fetal head deflection.**Objectives:** (1). To measure occiput spine angle during first stage of labor using Tran's abdominal ultrasound. (2). To determine whether this occiput spine angle has a relationship with course and outcome of labor.**Methods:** This was a prospective observational study conducted at the Obstetrics and Gynecology department Velammal Medical College and Research Institute, Madurai from January 2024 to June 2024. Women aged 18 (or) above with uncomplicated pregnancies at term (37 weeks and above) in cephalic presentation were subjected to trans abdominal ultrasound during the first stage of labor in fetuses with occipitoanterior and occipitotransverse position. The angle between fetal C1 cervical spine and occiput of fetal head was measured in the sagittal plane using trans abdominal ultrasound by two investigators. The mean value of the two measurements was taken as occiput spine angle (OSA). The correlation between the occiput spine angle and progression of labor along with mode of delivery were evaluated.**Results:** A total of 200 pregnant women were assessed. Out of which 143 participants underwent normal vaginal delivery and 57 study participants required obstetric interventions (44 lower segment cesarean and 13 instrumental deliveries). The mean value of occiput spine angle was $127^{\circ}.19 \pm 4^{\circ}.27$ during the active phase of the first stage of labor among the women who underwent normal vaginal delivery. The occiput spine angle was markedly lesser in women who underwent obstetric intervention. The mean OSA value for instrumental delivery was $111^{\circ}.46 \pm 2^{\circ}.93$. Whereas mean value of OSA for LSCS delivery was $110^{\circ}.61 \pm 3^{\circ}.37$. The inter observer reliability was moderate, identified by Cohen's kappa statistics (0.41-0.61) for measuring the occiput spine angle. A larger occiput spine angle measurement $>127^{\circ}$ showed shorter duration of a first and second stage of labor which resulted in normal vaginal deliveries ($P < 0.001$).**Conclusion:** Measuring occiput spine angle during first stage of labor using ultrasound is an effective predictor of course and outcome of labor. The $OSA > 126^{\circ}$ was associated with more incidence of normal vaginal delivery & shorter duration of first and second stage of labor whereas occiput spine angle less than 120° was associated with higher incidence of obstetric intervention & increased duration of first stage of labor. Narrower occiput spine angle would alert the obstetrician even in primary care center regarding labor dystocia and less likelihood of normal vaginal deliveries. Hence this newer ultrasound parameter occiput spine angle may be used as an adjunct to predict the course and outcome of labor thereby the need for obstetric interventions.**Keywords:** Occiput Spine Angle, Labor Dystocia, Fetal Head Attitude, First Stage Of Labor, Obstetric Interventions.

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Introduction

During the process of labor in cephalic presentation, the fetal head is well flexed which allows suboccipitobregmatic diameter to engage into the maternal pelvis [1]. In case of deflexed cephalic presentations, the labor is arrested which leads to cesarean delivery. A deflexed head is an important cause of obstructed labor. [2] There are 3 varieties of deflexed cephalic presentations, according to the degree of fetal head extension; they are named sinciput, brow, and face presentation. [3]

Achievement of normal vaginal delivery is not possible in the case of brow presentation where the presenting part diameter (mentovertical diameter) is 13.5cm which is greater than obstetric conjugate 11cm. [3] Evaluation of fetal station by clinical per vaginal examination is subjective and inaccurate with high inter-observer and intra-observer variability. Hence International Society of Ultrasound in Obstetrics and Gynecology recommends ultrasound assessment of fetal position and station during the active stage of labor which supports our traditional clinical per vaginal examination (digital examination). [4]

Other than these 3 varieties of fetal head deflexion, there are minor degrees of deflexion of the fetal head with respect to the trunk which is not clinically detected and may be sonographically documented by trans abdominal suprapubic ultrasound.

For a primigravida, rate of cervical dilatation <1.2cm/hour is defined as the prolonged 1st stage of labor whereas for a multigravida it is <1.5 cm/hr. Arrest of labor is defined as nonprogression of cervical dilation for more than 4 hours inspite of good uterine contraction (3-5 per 10 minutes).

The prolonged 2nd stage of labor is defined as fetal head descent <1 cm per hour in nulligravida & <2cm/hr in multigravida. [5] Second-stage labor arrest is defined as lack of fetal head descent after 2 or 3 hours of active pushing in the case of primigravida & after 1 or 2 hrs in case of multigravida irrespective of epidural analgesia.

Aim of the Study

1. To quantify the degree of fetal head deflection during 1st stage of labor by measuring Occiput Spine Angle using ultrasound.
2. To determine whether this occiput spine angle has a relationship with the course and outcome of labor.

Materials and Methods

This is an observational prospective study conducted in Velammal Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Madurai.

The study was approved by the institutional ethical committee and carried out in the department of obstetrics and gynecology labor room from January 2024 to June 2024 which involved 200 participants who met the following criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

Low risk pregnant women whose gestational age at (or) beyond 37 weeks, ≥ 18 years of age with singleton pregnancies in cephalic presentation. At the time of ultrasound examination cervical dilatation was between 3-6 cm and the head was not engaged (i.e.it did not cross the ischial spines) with regular uterine contractions. Informed and written consent was obtained from all the study participants.

Exclusion Criteria

The fetal head position is described as clock face using transabdominal ultrasound. Posterior occipital positions between 4 and 8 o'clock positions were excluded from our study. Other exclusion criteria as were:

- Multifetal gestation
- Malpresentation
- Previous uterine scars
- PROM >24 hrs
- Abnormal CTG
- Uterine anomalies
- Preterm labor <37 weeks of gestation
- Associated comorbidities for mother like overt DM on insulin,
- Severe preeclampsia.
- Those who didn't give consent for the study.

Occiput position determination was made by looking for following landmarks: fetal occiput, midline of fetal plane, fetal orbits & fetal cerebellum. [6] The position of occiput should be anterior (or) transverse. Patients should be in the active first stage of labor with good regular uterine contractions. The transducer placed in the suprapubic region of the women in supine position and occiput spine angle measurement was measured in between uterine contraction in order to avoid discomfort to the labouring women. The landmarks for identifying fetal head positions were fetal orbits, midline cerebral and cerebellum in case of occipitoposterior, occipitotransverse and occipitoanterior position respectively. [7]

In fetuses with occipito anterior or transverse position, a 2 dimensional sagittal view of fetal head and upper C1 cervical spine was acquired. In this image the angle formed by a line tangential to the first cervical vertebral spine and a line tangential to fetal occiput bone was measured. This angle is called Occiput Spine Angle (OSA). This angle was performed to quantify the attitude of fetal head with

respect to fetal trunk. In each case the angle was calculated by 2 independent investigators (one measurement is done by the principal investigator

and second measurement by any one of the co investigators). The mean value of the two measurements was calculated.

Figure 1: Demonstration of OSA in well flexed head

Figure 2: Demonstrating OSA in deflexed head

Since the investigator was not involved in the process of delivery of the study participant this ultrasound measurement did not alter the labor management. At the same time the ultrasound results were not informed to the obstetrician who was managing the patient. The labor outcome and mode of delivery was assessed in each case.

The obstetric intervention which was made due to abnormal or non-reassuring fetal heart rate was excluded because we wanted to assess the relationship between ultrasound index and risk of operative delivery due to prolonged labor or arrested labor.

Statistical Analysis

In the descriptive statistics, continuous variables were expressed in mean \pm SD and the categorical variables were expressed in frequency and

percentage. In the analytical statistics, Chi Square test and ANOVA was applied.

P value 0.05 was found to be statistically significant. Interobserver reliability was identified by Cohen's kappa statistics (0.41 – 0.61 = moderate agreement).

Result

Total 200 pregnant women were recruited in the study. The mean age of the participants was 24.52 ± 3.8 , the minimum age was 18 and the maximum age was 39 years. Term pregnancy was 88% (176) and the rest 12% (24) were post-dated pregnancy. 74% (148) were primigravida, 26 % (52) were multigravida. Out of 200, 58% n=116 had spontaneous onset of labor, 42% n=84 had induction of labor.

Table 1: Shows clinical, demographic and ultrasound variables in all three modes of deliveries

Parameters	Mode of Delivery			F	P value
	Normal vaginal delivery (n= 143)	LSCS (n= 44)	Instrumental delivery (n= 13)		
Age	24.92 ± 4.06	23.23 ± 3.1	24.54 ± 3.43	3.28	0.039
Duration of 1st stage of labor (in minutes)	346.97 ± 126.7	577.52 ± 156.8	423.07 ± 135.85	49.61	<0.001
Progression of labor (cm /hr)	1.3406 ± 0.596	0.5451 ± 0.256	$0.9115 \pm .309$	38.99	<0.001
Duration of 2nd stage of labor (in minutes)	47.48 ± 31.29	155 ± 24.47	150.15 ± 30.07	133.08	<0.001
Cervical dilatation at the time of OSA measurement (cm)	$3.82 \pm .82$	$3.39 \pm .65$	4.08 ± 1.1	5.92	<0.001
Cervical length(cm)	0.70 ± 0.90	0.75 ± 1	0.47 ± 1.15	0.46	0.63
Head station	$-2.12 \pm .658$	$-2.7 \pm .55$	$-2.8 \pm .37$	20.283	<0.001
Occiput spine angle (in degrees) (OSA 1)	126.91 ± 4.79	110.48 ± 3.82	111 ± 3.48	264.42	<0.001
Occiput spine angle (in degrees) (OSA 2)	127.55 ± 4.24	111.55 ± 3.28	112.54 ± 4.05	310.42	<0.001
Occiput spine angle (in degrees) (Mean value)	127.19 ± 4.27	110.61 ± 3.37	111.46 ± 2.93	338.19	<0.001
Baby birth weight (in Kgs)	2.97 ± 0.38	2.95 ± 0.46	3.11 ± 0.3	0.821	0.442

Out of 200 pregnant women 143 underwent spontaneous vaginal delivery whereas lower segment cesarean delivery (or) instrumental was performed in 44 and 12 women respectively. The indication for cesarean were CPD in 19 patients, second stage labor arrest in 8 patients and non-progress of labor in 17 patients. The mean cervical dilatation at the time of occiput spine angle measurement were 3.82, 3.39 and 4.08 centimeter

for women who delivered by normal vaginal delivery, cesarean and instrumental delivery respectively. The mean fetal head station which was assessed by digital examination at the time of occiput spine angle measurement were -2.12, -2.7 and -2.8 in women who underwent normal vaginal delivery, cesarean and instrumental delivery respectively.

Figure 3: Demonstrating correlation between duration of first stage of labor with various mode of delivery and its corresponding mean OSA

The mean duration of first stage of labor in pregnant woman who underwent normal vaginal delivery was 346.97±126.7minutes. The mean duration of first stage of labor in instrument delivery and LSCS delivery was 423.07±135.85 and 577.52±156.8 minute's .The mean duration of second stage of labor in women who underwent normal vaginal delivery was 47.48±31.29minutes and that of instrumental and cesarean deliveries were 150.15±30.7 and 155 ± 24.47 minutes respectively. The mean birth weights were 2.97±0.38 Kg, 2.95±0.46 Kg, 3.11±0.3Kg (p value 0.442) in women who underwent normal vaginal

delivery, cesarean and instrumental delivery respectively. Among the 1 minute APGAR score, mild respiratory depression was found in 11.2% (16) of normal delivery, 6.8% (3) in LSCS and 69.2% (9) in instrumental delivery. The difference was statistically significant (p value< 0.05). The APGAR at 5 minutes improved in all babies except with only 1 baby (7.7%) of instrumental delivery had mild respiratory depression. The Apgar score of the baby has a significant correlation with NICU admission (p<0.05). Among instrumental delivered babies 30.8% (4), in LSCS 20.5% (9) and in normal labor 4.2% (6) babies had NICU admission.

Figure 4: Bar chart representing mode of delivery in primigravida and multigravida

Figure 5: Bar diagram representing mean OSA values in different mode of delivery

The mean value of occiput spine angle was 127°.19 ±4°.27 during the active phase of the first stage of labor among the women who underwent normal vaginal delivery. The OSA was markedly lesser in women who underwent obstetric intervention. The mean OSA value for instrumental delivery and LSCS was 111°.46±2°.93 and 110°.61±3°.37 respectively.

Table 2: Cross tab between obstetric code and present mode of delivery

Obstetric Score	Present mode of delivery			X ²	P value
	Normal vaginal delivery(143)	Instrumental delivery (n= 13)	LSCS (n= 44)		
Primigravida	93 (65 %)	11 (84.6%)	44 (100 %)	37.3	<0.001
Multigravida	50 (35 %)	2 (15.4%)	0		

Table 3: Comparison of occiput spinal angle with mode of delivery

OSA (degree)	Mode of delivery			X ²	P value
	Normal vaginal delivery (n= 143)	LSCS (n= 44)	Instrumental delivery (n= 13)		
Less than 120	11 (7.7%)	44 (100%)	13 (100%)	154.7	<0.001
121-126	57 (39.9%)	0	0		
More than 127	75 (37.5%)	0	0		

Figure 6: Bar diagram representing comparison between OSA with various modes of delivery

Among the 68 patients who had OSA < 120, 44 underwent LSCS, 13 underwent instrumental deliveries and only 11 had normal vaginal deliveries.

Discussion

The principal findings of this study are

1. Occiput– spine angle measurement is feasible and reproducible using a non-invasive modality by ultrasound.
2. There is a positive correlation between fetal head station (which was found by clinical digital examination) and occiput spine angle measurement during active first stage of labor
3. Occiput spine angle measurement is inversely proportional to the duration of first and second stage of labor.
4. Shorter occiput spine angle correlates significantly with risk of labor arrest which mandates instrumental or cesarean delivery.

Shorter occiput spine angle denotes deflexed attitude of fetal head during the first stage of labor. Hence there is relative cephalopelvic disproportion due to increased engaging diameter of the presenting part. Ultimately this results in labor arrest and obstetric interventions.

In search of literature, in Tullio Ghi et al study, out of 108 pregnant women, 79 underwent normal delivery and 29 had obstetric interventions. They found significant differences between different variables in women who underwent cesarean and normal delivery as follows lower parity (5.3%vs43% $P<0.01$) smaller occiput spine angle (121 ± 10.5 vs 127 ± 9.4 , $P=0.03$).prolonged duration of first stage of labor (505 ± 259 vs 274.1 ± 168.6 $P<0.001$) more birth weight (3635 ± 391 VS 3335 ± 479 , $p0.01$). In their study there was no significant difference between the women who were delivered by normal and cesarean in terms of age (32.3 vs 34.2 $P0.22$) and gestational age (39.5 VS 39.7 $P0.44$). Our study results were comparable with that of Tullio Ghi et al study. In our study for women who delivered normally the mean occiput spine angle was 127.19 ± 4.27 ($P<0.001$) which is comparable to Tullio Ghi et al study 127 ± 9.4 ($P0.03$).In their study they concluded that the occiput spine angle >125 degree significantly associated with shorter duration of labor (95% CI 1.07-2.45, $P=0.02$) and also smaller occiput spine angles are at more risk of operative deliveries. [10]

Our study correlates with two other studies conducted by J.Shetty and Federico Bellussi. In a study by Federico Bellussi et al, they demonstrated a significant correlation between deflexed fetal head and cesarean section deliveries regardless of fetal occiput position(adjusted odds ratio 5.83;95 % confidence interval 2.47-13.73).In study conducted by J.Shetty et al, they recruited 99

pregnant women, out of which 63 underwent normal delivery, 36 required obstetric intervention (28 - cesarean section, 8 - instrumental delivery)the mean value of occiput spine angle was 127 ± 8.2 in women who underwent normal delivery. In cesarean (or) forceps delivery the angle was significantly narrower 120 ± 6.2 . They concluded the occiput spine angle had a cutoff value of 125 below which the probability of cesarean was higher with sensitivity of 94% and a specificity of 96%. [11,12]

A multicentric study by Andrea Dall' Asta et al showed that wider occiput spine angle (126 ± 14 vs 115 ± 24 ; $P<0.01$) had vaginal deliveries compared with those who delivered by obstetric invention because of labor dystocia. [13] In the study conducted among 380 pregnant women by Hina Hanif Mughad et al the mean OSA for vaginal delivery was 131.9 ± 35 and that for operative delivery were 118.6 ± 4.7 respectively. They found women with occiput spine angle values $<126^\circ$ had more risk of operative deliveries. In our study, there was a higher incidence of cesarean delivery with mean OSA value $111^\circ.55\pm 3^\circ.28$) P value of <0.001 . In contrast to our results a study conducted by Salman et al, mean OSA of $\leq 118^\circ$ had a higher incidence of cesarean delivery with sensitivity (90.9%) specificity (83.9%) positive predictive value (97.9%).

In a similar study conducted by Zeinab Yousef Hassan EL Sheshtawey et al found out smaller occiput spine angle $<126^\circ$ had significant risk of cesarean section. Also they found cutoff value of occiput spine angle as 133° below which there was an increased chance of fetomaternal complications

In the study conducted by Ahmad Mohamed Abd elf Attah et al in 200 pregnant women, they found the occiput spine angle cutoff value as 126° was safe for normal delivery. Also they found abnormality in progress of labor which required obstetrics interventions was higher (75.8%) in case of occiput spine angle value less than 126° as compared to that of occiput spine angle value more than 126° (11.4%) They found respiratory distress for newborn was 18.2% vs 1.2% when compared to the Occiput Spine angle value was less than 126° and more than 126° . [14]

Hesham Mohammed Fathy et al conducted similar study in 200 women, they found positive correlation between occiput spine angle and fetal head station during first stage of labor and lesser the occiput spine angle more was the chances of obstructed labor which necessitates operative deliveries. Keerthi Somu et al studied 145 nulliparous women during active phase of first stage of labor, they found mean occiput spine angle measurement was less in cesarean group when

compared to that of normal labor group ($116^{\circ}.25 \pm 9^{\circ}.2$ versus $126^{\circ}.53 \pm 11^{\circ}.1$ $p < 0.01$) Whereas in Ahmed Maged AM et al study they demonstrated significantly prolonged duration of 1st and 2nd stage of labor when OSA was $< 126^{\circ}.8$. Women with OSA $< 126^{\circ}$ had higher risk of operative deliveries (46.3% vs 5.7%) perineal tears (10.4 vs 5.1%) vaginal tears (22.4% vs 6.3%) when compared to those with angle $> 126^{\circ}$. In our study only 3.5% of women with shorter OSA had third degree perineal tear. This may be attributed to good perineal support. [15]

Viola Ying Tze chan et al performed a transperineal ultrasound to assess fetal head station in sagittal or mid axial plane during labor. They found the angle of progression AoP of 145° significantly associated with successful vaginal delivery whereas AoP 120° had increased risk of assisted vaginal delivery. Even though this ultrasound parameter is a good predictor of labor dystocia, it can be measured only at second stage of labor after full cervical dilatation.

Whereas in our study there is a chance of early detection of abnormal labor progression in active first stage of labor which gives us an additional advantage.[16,17,18]

Strength & Limitation

Our study performed a non-invasive modality to measure the occiput spine angle in the labor room itself by using TAS. Almost no dropouts were noted in our study.

Limitation to our study is, we excluded occipitoposterior position which is a common position in about 30% of fetuses in the 1st stage of labour. Because of the posterior position of the C1 cervical spine in the occipitoposterior position, the measurement of OSA is not technically feasible.

Conclusion

We have described that occiput spine angle is a new sonographic measurement that correlates well with abnormal labor progression warranting instrumental and cesarean deliveries. We can also able to quantify the degree of fetal head deflection during first stage of labor accurately. The occiput spine angle with $> 126^{\circ}$ was associated with more incidence of vaginal deliveries and shorter duration of first and second of labor. Therefore OSA can be used as a good predictor for the progress and outcome of labor.

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